

A Deep Learning Framework for Missing Information Imputation in Traffic Crash Records

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Abstract

Traffic crash records frequently lack complete information, often because the sporadic nature of incidents prevents timely recording of relevant details, and victims or witnesses may be reluctant to fill out comprehensive information forms. This prevalent under-reporting or partial reporting significantly impedes precise traffic risk prediction and the classification of crash severity. In response to these data challenges, this paper introduces an integrated imputation-classification framework. We employ a deep learning (DL)-based edge-level graph representation learning method, specifically designed to impute missing information in contributing factors through graph edge value prediction. Our framework’s efficacy is demonstrated using a comprehensive dataset of incident records from 2018 to 2022, sourced from the UK Department for Transport’s STATS19 data. Notably, this approach is the first to be proven to outperform existing methods in traffic crash data imputation, thereby significantly enhancing the accuracy and reliability of traffic risk prediction and crash severity classification in traffic crash analysis.

KEYWORDS: Traffic Crash, Deep Learning Imputation, Contrastive Learning, Missing Information, Traffic Safety.

1 Introduction

Traffic crashes are increasingly recognized as a major threat to urban sustainability. Not only do they lead to tragic loss of life, but they also incur substantial economic costs. These incidents present complex challenges, impacting citizens’ well-being and underscoring the need for advanced prevention strategies (Imprialou and Quddus, 2019). Current research in traffic crash prevention

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and casualty severity prediction often focuses on methodological sophistication and accuracy enhancement. Yet, despite advancements in prediction model accuracy, the success of data-driven models heavily relies on the quality and completeness of the input data. Traffic crashes, inherently sporadic, are prone to underreporting, resulting in inconsistent and incomplete data (Abay, 2015).

In the realm of statistical modelling, for example, Zhu and Srinivasan (2011) treated 'missing' data as a distinct category within each factor, revealing the significant impact of 'missing data' dummy variables on severity assessments and highlighting how data completeness influences results. Meanwhile, in machine learning (ML) models, designed to handle missing or partial data, a common approach in severity classification has been to treat these missing elements as errors or noise, to be removed during data cleaning (Mohammadpour et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2019). However, this list-wise elimination of incomplete observations can introduce inaccuracies by producing less representative sample sets and altering the distribution of raw data. Particularly, when simultaneously considering both active and non-active travel modes within a unified records table, such as vehicle information alongside pedestrian injury incidents, it becomes crucial to retain essential information (Tyndall, 2024). For example, pedestrian records inherently lack details about automatic vehicle features. Directly eliminating these data points would omit critical context, underscoring the importance of a nuanced approach to data imputation that acknowledges the distinct characteristics of each travel mode.

To address these data challenges, this paper proposes an innovative integrated imputation classification framework. We introduce a deep learning (DL)-based edge-level graph representation learning method at the core of our approach. This method is crafted to impute missing information in records by predicting the missing values of absent graph edges. Taking advantage of this technique, our framework aims to improve the integrity and precision of crash record data, which is crucial for effective analysis of traffic crashes and subsequent interventions. The code was implicitly written with Python and is derived from the GRAPE project ¹.

2 Data and Method

In Figure 1, our proposed data imputation method is detailed. Initially, we construct a bipartite graph, using non-missing column values as embeddings for traffic crash nodes, and treating columns with missing data as column nodes, whose embeddings are derived from one-hot encoding of their names. Subsequently, two Transformers are employed to encode both incident and column nodes, leading to the generation of edge spatiotemporal embeddings. At this stage, we calculate the reconstruction loss. To bolster the model's robustness, we implement graph contrastive learning, augmenting the dataset with positive and negative samples and computing the contrastive learning loss. The model is optimized by combining the edge reconstruction loss and the InfoNCE loss, processed simultaneously.

We used the STATS19 dataset, published by the Department for Transport, UK, for our traffic accident data. This data set was compiled by merging the accidents, drivers, and casualty tables.

¹<https://github.com/maxiaoba/GRAPE>

Figure 1: Framework of the imputation model

It could be downloaded from the *STATS19* R package(Lovelace et al., 2019). Our final data set comprised 416,981 records of driver-involved injuries in Great Britain, spanning January 2018 to December 2022, and included 36 factors. The data distribution, predominantly skewed in most columns and particularly in categorical variables, is illustrated in Figure 2.

In particular, 27 variables exhibit inherent missing values, a consequence of the nature of police reporting, as detailed in Figure 3.

In our results comparison, we evaluated our imputation model across seven different missing data rates, ranging from 10% to 70%. We benchmarked our model against the following baselines:

1. **Class Imputation (CI)**: A traditional column-wise single imputation method, CI distinguishes between numerical and categorical columns. It imputes missing values using the mean value for numerical columns and the mode value for categorical columns.
2. **Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE)**: This method operates as a sequential regression multiple imputation approach. It predicts each missing value based solely on the information from existing values in the dataset by multiple regression processes.
3. **K-nearest Neighbours (KNN)**: KNN is an unsupervised learning ML method that imputes missing values based on the average values of the k nearest variables. These variables are identified through Euclidean Distance measurements surrounding the missing value.
4. **Bipartite graph Learning (Bi-GNN)**: Bi-GNN, representing the state-of-the-art (SOTA) in DL imputation, is an extension of GraphSAGE (Hamilton et al., 2017). It adapts traditional

graph representation to a bipartite graph, specifically for imputing missing values as edge values (You et al., 2020).

We evaluate our imputation method using two common evaluation metrics (Li et al., 2020), namely, the correct imputation rate (CIR) and the mean absolute error (MAE). MAE evaluates the accuracy of predicted numerical values against actual values, with lower scores indicating better imputation for continuous variables.

Table 1: Metrics for Data Imputation and Imbalanced Classification

Category	Metric	Formula
Data Imputation	MAE	$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i - \hat{y}_i $
	CIR	$\frac{C}{N} \times 100\%$

Hereby, we define several key variables: N represents the total number of observations in the dataset. C denotes the count of values that are correctly imputed. For each observation, y_i indicates the actual value of the i -th observation, while \hat{y}_i represents the imputed (or predicted) value for the same observation.

3 Results and Discussion

In the imputation phase, we present results using the metrics, as shown in Table 2, averaged over five-fold iterations. This approach illustrates our model’s performance across varying missing rates. Notably, our imputation model consistently outperforms both traditional ML models and state-of-the-art (SOTA) DL imputation models across the seven missing rates. In our dataset, which includes 34 categorical features out of 36, our model’s CIR achieved an accuracy of no less than 94.74% for categorical features, even with a 70% missing rate. The stability of our model’s accuracy is evident, with only a 4.5% decrease from the 10% to 70% missing rates, surpassing the second-best baseline model, CI, which shows a decrease of 8.72%. Furthermore, in cases where certain categorical variables exhibit skewed distributions, with some values predominantly occurring, the CI method emerges as the second-best performer. This effectiveness can be attributed to CI’s ability to capture and leverage these dominant values for imputation purposes. Specifically, in variables where a few categories are overwhelmingly represented, the CI method efficiently utilizes these prevalent categories to predict missing values, thereby aligning well with the actual distribution of the data. In terms of numerical data imputation, our model exhibits high accuracy with minimal variance, even in scenarios with high missing rates. Notably, it demonstrates more than 9.1% lower MAE compared to KNN models at 60% and 70% missing rates.

The MICE model demonstrates the least effectiveness across all missing rates in our study. As described by Westermeier and Grabka (2016) and Vidotto et al. (2020), MICE functions as a sequential regression model, primarily utilizing linear main effects. It treats variables with missing data as outcomes, regressing them sequentially against other dataset variables. However, its efficacy is limited in datasets predominated by categorical data and those that do not adhere to the Missing

at Random (MAR) assumption or exhibit complex global correlations, as seen in our dataset (Figure 2).

Table 2: Performance comparison of Imputation methods. Red font indicates the best-performing model, while blue signifies the second-best in baselines.

(a) Missing Rate from 10% to 40%

Method	Missing Rate							
	10%		20%		30%		40%	
	MAE	CIR	MAE	CIR	MAE	CIR	MAE	CIR
<i>CI</i>	0.0180	98.53%	0.0361	97.21%	0.0541	95.15%	0.0722	94.66%
<i>KNN</i>	0.0138	98.47%	0.0289	96.77%	0.0450	94.97%	0.0617	93.10%
<i>Bi - GNN</i>	0.0181	98.25%	0.0362	96.51%	0.0542	94.76%	0.0724	93.01%
<i>MICE</i>	0.0205	98.19%	0.0439	96.08%	0.0697	93.55%	0.1398	88.28%
<i>Ours</i>	0.0124	99.24%	0.0271	98.45%	0.0355	97.74%	0.0469	96.99 %

(b) Missing Rate from 50% to 70%

Method	Missing Rate					
	50%		60%		70%	
	MAE	CIR	MAE	CIR	MAE	CIR
<i>CI</i>	0.0903	91.73%	0.1083	90.44%	0.1264	89.81%
<i>KNN</i>	0.0791	91.14%	0.0970	89.14%	0.1151	87.12%
<i>Bi - GNN</i>	0.0905	91.26%	0.1085	89.52%	0.1266	87.78%
<i>MICE</i>	0.1642	86.42%	0.1829	81.92%	0.2417	76.95%
<i>Ours</i>	0.0588	96.24%	0.0697	95.49%	0.0817	94.74%

4 Conclusion

This paper showcases the effectiveness of our DL method in imputing missing information in traffic crash data, even at high missing rates. Our comprehensive framework, a novel introduction to the crash information management domain, shifts the focus towards data augmentation and completeness. This approach not only addresses existing gaps but also sets a new precedent in the utilization of DL techniques for enhancing data integrity in traffic safety research.

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6 Biography

Xiaowei Gao, a fourth-year PhD student at UCL’s SpaceTimeLab, focuses on traffic safety management and crash risk prediction. He interns at the Department for Transport’s TAMS team, UK.

Xinke Jiang, a first-year MRes student at Peking University, China, researches Knowledge Graphs, Graph Neural Networks, and Spatial-Temporal Mining.

James Haworth, Associate Professor at UCL's SpaceTimeLab, specializes in machine learning and AI for spatiotemporal data, with applications in transportation, geodemographics, and crime.

Huanfa Chen, Associate Professor in Spatial Data Science at UCL's CASA, focuses on geocomputation techniques including neural networks, heuristic search, and agent-based simulation.

Ilya Ilyankou, a first-year PhD student at UCL's SpaceTimeLab, investigates conversational systems for complex routing, exploring language model adaptations for geospatial data. His research is funded by the Ordnance Survey.

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Figure 2: Distribution of factors

Figure 3: Missing Rate in each column.